

Palladium(II) Chelates of α -Oximinoacetetarylamide Salicylhydrazones

M. M. PATEL and M. R. PATEL*

Department of Chemistry, Sardar Patel University, Vallabh Vidyanagar-388 120 Gujarat.

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A number of palladium(II) chelates of the type Pd(OAASH)₂ where, OAASH represents salicylhydrazones of α -oximinoacetoacetanilide, *o*-toluidide, *p*-toluidide, *o*-chloroanilide, *m*-chloroanilide, *p*-chloroanilide, *o*-aniside, *p*-aniside, (2,4)-xylidide, (2,4)-dimethoxyanilide and *p*-phenitidide have been studied. All the chelates are diamagnetic and their infrared spectra suggest the coordination of these ligands through nitrogens of the oximino and salicyl hydrazide moieties. The square planar stereochemistry around the Pd(II) ion in the chelates have been proposed.

IN continuation of our previous work¹⁻⁶, the present paper describes the preparation and characterisation of Pd(II) chelates of α -oximinoacetetarylamide salicylhydrazones.

Experimental

Preparation of the Pd(II) chelate of α -oximinoacetanilide salicylhydrazone :

10 ml aqueous solution of Pd(II) chloride (0.05M) was gradually added to 25 ml alcoholic solution (2%) of α -oximinoacetanilide salicylhydrazone and acidified with dil. HCl. The mixture was diluted to about 100 ml with distilled

water and digested on water bath for half an hour, the bright yellow precipitates obtained were filtered, washed with hot water and aqueous ethanol (1 : 1), and dried in an oven at 110°.

The Pd(II) chelates of the other α -oximinoacetetarylamide salicylhydrazones of the series were prepared in the similar manner. The m.p., colour, elemental analysis and composition of the chelates are given in Table 1.

The infra-red spectra of the ligands and their Pd(II) chelates in KBr pellets and magnetic measurements of the Pd(II) chelates were recorded.

TABLE I— PALLADIUM CHELATES OF α -OXIMINOACETACET-ARYLAMIDE SALICYLHYDRAZONES

No.	R	Composition	Colour	m.p.°C (decomp.)	% Palladium		% Nitrogen	
					Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
1.	H	C ₃₄ H ₃₀ N ₈ O ₈ Pd	Bright Yellow	307	13.45	13.60	14.16	14.27
2.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	C ₃₆ H ₃₄ N ₈ O ₈ Pd	" "	303	13.13	13.12	13.92	13.78
3.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	C ₃₆ H ₃₄ N ₈ O ₈ Pd	" "	310	13.05	13.12	13.72	13.78
4.	<i>o</i> -Cl	C ₃₄ H ₂₈ N ₈ O ₈ Cl ₂ Pd	" "	312	12.45	12.50	13.30	13.12
5.	<i>m</i> -Cl	C ₃₄ H ₂₈ N ₈ O ₈ Cl ₂ Pd	" "	305	12.41	12.50	13.24	13.12
6.	<i>p</i> -Cl	C ₃₄ H ₂₈ N ₈ O ₈ Cl ₂ Pd	Golden Yellow	314	12.43	12.50	13.04	13.12
7.	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	C ₃₆ H ₃₄ N ₈ O ₁₀ Pd	" "	295	12.54	12.63	13.40	13.26
8.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	C ₃₆ H ₃₄ N ₈ O ₁₀ Pd	Red	312	12.58	12.63	13.18	13.26
9.	<i>m</i> -2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	C ₃₈ H ₃₈ N ₈ O ₈ Pd	Golden Yellow	308	12.61	12.70	13.38	13.32
10.	2,4-(OCH ₃) ₂	C ₃₈ H ₃₈ N ₈ O ₁₂ Pd	Red	303	11.61	11.67	12.35	12.25
11.	<i>p</i> -OC ₂ H ₅	C ₃₈ H ₃₈ N ₈ O ₁₀ Pd	Red	296	12.15	12.22	12.95	12.85

*For Correspondence.

Results and Discussion

Magnetic Susceptibility : All the Pd(II) chelates were found to be diamagnetic. Hence the square planar structure for the chelates has been suggested.

Infrared Spectra : The assignment of important infrared bands in free ligands and in their chelates are given in the Table 2. The band at 2600-2632

evident that ligands as well as chelates in the solid state are mostly in the associated form. The probable associations are due to H-bonding between carbonyl group and hydrogens of an amide and salicylhydrazide moieties. The strong band around 3300 cm^{-1} is considered to be due to trans associated form. The strong bands in the ligands and chelates around 1620 and 1680 cm^{-1} , 1540 cm^{-1} and 1310 and 1235 cm^{-1} are attributed to amide I,

TABLE 2— IMPORTANT INFRARED BANDS OF LIGANDS AND THEIR Pd(II) CHELATES (cm^{-1})

No.	$\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$	$\nu\text{N}-\text{O}$	$\nu\text{O}-\text{H}$	$\nu\text{N}-\text{H}$ -(Secondary) Associated	$\nu\text{N}-\text{N}$
1	1560 s	965 s	2611 mb	3311 s, 3096 s	1036 m
1A	1550 s	1138 s	-	3289 s, 3125 s	1072 s
2	1563 s	966 s	2632 mb	3300 s, 3106 sb	1042 m
2A	1550 s	1130 s	-	3333 b, 3115 m	1072 s
3	1558 sb	966 s	2625 mb	3300 s, 3067 sb	1038 m
3A	1548 sb	1134 s	-	3322 w, 3106 m	1075 m
4	1563 sb	970 s	2632 mb	3311 s, 3086 sb	1040 sm
4A	1548 sb	1136 s	-	3311 w, 3125 m	1075
5	1563 sb	973 s	2632 mb	3300 s, 3067 s	1040 s
5A	1550 sb	1136 s	-	3300 m, 3106 m	107 2
6	1563 sb	970 s	2618 mb	3300 s, 3077 s	1040 m
6A	1550 sb	1134 s	-	3279 m, 3125 m	1073 s
7	1563 sb	970 s	2611 mb	3300 s, 3067 s	1040 m
7A	1550 sb	1130 ms	-	3300 m, 3067 m	1075 s
8	1563 sb	970 s	2600 mb	3300 s, 3049 s	1038 m
8A	1558 sb	1136 s	-	3311 w, 3125 m	1073 s
9	1563 s	970 s	2632 mb	3268 s, 3076 s	1047 s
9A	1555 s	1142 s	-	3333 m, 3145 m	1078 s
10	1538 s	970 s	2618 mb	3300 s, 3077 s	1036 s
10A	1524 sb	1136 s	-	3300 m, 3106 m	1070 m
11	1563 s	970 s	2620 mb	3322 s, 3030 m	1040 w
11A	1550 s	1136 s	-	3311 m, 3125 b	1070 m

s=strong, m=medium, w=weak, b=broad, v=very

Serial numbers are according to Table 1 ; numbers without letter A are the ligands and with letter A are the corresponding chelates.

cm^{-1} appears in the ligands but does not appear in the corresponding chelates which suggests the presence of intramolecular H-bond in the ligands⁷. The absence of this band in the chelates is the indication of the replacement of hydrogen of oximino group by metal ion. The strong band at 965–973 cm^{-1} in the ligands is attributed to N-O stretch. In the chelates this band shifts to 1130-1142 cm^{-1} which suggests the coordination through nitrogen of oximino group⁸⁻¹¹. The strong band around 1538-1563 cm^{-1} in the ligands belongs to C=N stretching frequency. In the chelates this band appears around 1524-1558 cm^{-1} . The lowering of the C=N stretching frequency is indicating the coordination through I-nitrogen of salicylhydrazide moiety. The N-N band around 1036-1047 cm^{-1} in the ligands shifts to the higher frequency in the chelates. The magnitude of this positive shift (30-37 cm^{-1}) shows the monodentate linkage of N-N residue as a shift 50 cm^{-1} is usually observed in case of bidentate linking of N-N¹². The infrared spectra of the ligands and chelates reveal bands around 3300, 3100 and 3500 cm^{-1} indicating secondary trans association and free N-H vibrations of amides respectively¹³. From the Table 2 it is

amide II and amide III bands, as associated and free forms respectively¹³.

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